

Panel discussion: Can design contribute to subjective well-being and happiness? Multidisciplinary insights and experiences

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Topic This panel session focuses on subjective well-being / happiness and the contribution that design can have herein.

‘Happiness’ and ‘well-being’ are one of the major, if not the ultimate, life goal. Studying happiness is important, relevant and timely because firstly, there seems to be a societal need to focus on this topic. Secondly, it is highly relevant from an economic perspective, as happy people seem to be successful in many domains of life, whereby these successes are at least in part due to their happiness (Lyubomirsky et al., 2005). Thirdly, happiness has also become an issue on the political agenda.

The last decades, researchers from diverse disciplines have tried to point to the essence of well-being and happiness. In addition, the last few years, different researchers from various design disciplines begun to investigate whether their discipline can contribute to happiness, and, if so, how this contribution can look like. However, to date, there is no consensus on the conceptualization of well-being and happiness (Lyubomirsky, 2007 ; Sheldon & Lyubomirsky, 2007 ; Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013). All design research with a focus on well-being and happiness that is currently being performed, thus can be considered to be pioneering work.

Purpose

Aim:

- (i) Develop an understanding of approaches employed in different design disciplines regarding design for well-being and happiness
- (ii) Discuss and disseminate insights and experiences
- (iii) Support further growth of field of knowledge

Relevance for the D&E conference:

- (i) Bring together a multidisciplinary team of experts regarding design for well-being and happiness
- (ii) Dissemination of knowledge regarding the question how design can contribute to happiness

Relevance for the community:

- (i) Help this field of knowledge to further evolve: dissemination of knowledge can enhance future research and collaboration initiatives
- (ii) In the long run: make more people happy through design

Keywords *Subjective well-being and happiness, Assessment, Enabling activities, Multidisciplinary reflections and insights*